

Applying Digital Twins to Optical Networks with Cloud-native SDN Controllers

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Abstract—The use of Network Digital Twins (NDT) in optical networks is a promising development that can improve network optimization, decision-making, and testing. The proposed architecture that utilizes SDN controllers to deploy NDTs presents a novel approach to achieving these benefits. The virtual representation of the physical optical network provided by the NDT allows for the testing of different scenarios and the validation of specific behaviors before their implementation in the physical network, such as network optimization. This approach can help network operators identify potential issues and optimize the network's performance, resulting in cost savings and improved user experiences.

In this paper, the authors present an architecture for optical networks that utilizes SDN controllers to deploy Network Digital Twins. The proposed architecture provides a virtual representation of the physical optical network, allowing for the introduction of several use cases. For example, the proposed solution enables the validation of dynamically deployed novel optical light-paths in the underlying physical network. The authors evaluate key aspects of their proposed solution, including optical NDT deployment and tear down times, as well as the latency required to modify the NDT with information from the physical network.

Index Terms—Network Digital Twin, SDN controller, optical networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ongoing digital transformation is introducing a wide range of technologies, which are gradually replacing manual processes with digital ones in various industries. In this context, Digital Twins (DT) have emerged as a critical tool, defined as "the real-time representation of physical entities in the digital world" [1]. DT provides real-time interaction and virtual-reality interrelation, facilitating process optimization and iterative operation. By creating virtual replicas of physical assets or processes, DT allows companies to simulate, analyze, and optimize different scenarios before implementing changes in the physical world. This virtual-reality interrelation enables operators to interact with the virtual model and make informed decisions. In intelligent manufacturing, DT can be used to optimize the production process, reducing downtime and improving product quality [1].

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In order to provide network services to 5G connections located at the disaggregated cell site gateway, optical networks are essential. Transport network slices are virtualized segments or portions of a physical transport network that are dedicated to meeting specific requirements and providing tailored services for a particular use case or customer. Through transport network slicing [2], it is possible to allocate dedicated transport network slices to support multiple 3GPP network slices, including Enhanced Mobile Broadband, Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications, and massive Machine Type Communications. 3GPP network slices consist of RAN, transport and core network slices.

Network operations and maintenance are intricate and usually involve human intervention. Various factors need to be taken into account, ranging from physical impairments affecting the provided light paths to traffic scheduling and forecasting. As new connectivity services are being introduced on the network, it becomes increasingly challenging to avoid interfering with existing services while minimizing trial costs. Currently, planning tools that use Quality of Transmission (QoT) estimation techniques [3] are being used to analyze the network statically. While many implementations of SDN controllers can provide data analytics of the current traffic status for traffic scheduling or forecasting, they lack dynamism and closed-control loop behavior based on the analyzed results. Adding more dynamism to networks would require the network to expose a full set of data primitives, which has been also the scope of multiple standards [4].

By applying Digital Twin technology to networks and creating a virtual representation of physical network facilities that goes beyond emulation (e.g., using a virtual representation of the network with real time updates from measured physical data), it is possible to build a network digital twin (NDT) platform. With virtualization techniques, each network topology can be digitally replicated [5]. The NDT can facilitate closed-loop network management throughout the entire life-cycle, including deployment and emulation, visualized assessment, physical deployment, and continuous verification.

The NDT's global, systemic, and consistent view of the network enables several use cases for network operators, and to some extent, end-users. Network operators can safely enforce network planning policies and deployment procedures without jeopardizing the daily operation of the physical network [6]. NDT also facilitates closed-loop network management throughout the entire life cycle, from deployment and emulation to visualized assessment, physical deployment, and

continuous verification. One of the benefits of digital twin networks is the safer testing of innovative network capabilities, including "what if" scenarios [7].

Fig. 1. Network Digital Twins information flows

The exchange of information between a physical object and its NDT in both directions is essential for developing a successful NDT. As shown in Figure 1, the virtual twin must adapt quickly to changes in its physical counterpart (mapping), while the physical object must respond promptly to interventions occurring in the virtual twin (feedback). To impart cognition/intelligence to the NDT, models must be obtained through NDT training. This training can be done using synthetic data or data from small-scale testbeds, or by monitoring and streaming data from the actual physical network using applications available at the physical network Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller. The updated models can then be fed into the NDT and their effectiveness re-evaluated [8]. By acquiring models through NDT training, the NDT system can develop an understanding of the patterns, correlations, and characteristics inherent in the network data. These models act as representations of the network and its functioning.

The network SDN controller plays a vital role in this process by providing standard interfaces to manage and control data plane activities of optical networks, including the IP and optical layers [2]. SDN controllers offer network programmability and serve as enablers of NDT, and some of their critical features include the ability to collect data streams, provide network topology, and support easy integration of novel applications. Therefore, it is essential that the SDN controller is easy to integrate, making micro-service architecture a better fit for this purpose. Using cloud-native applications offers several advantages, and the ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) is a cloud-native SDN controller that we propose for enabling NDT. Using SDN controllers deployed as cloud-native applications provides benefits such as increased modularity, reliability, and faster development of specific applications [2].

In [9], the concept of an Optical Networks Digital Twin was introduced, which employs digital twin technology to simplify, automate, and improve the resilience of network operation and maintenance for network operators. Real-time data from

the physical network is essential for an optical NDT, which can be used for real-time quality of transmission estimation. Optical physical impairments need to be taken into account when considering the specifics of an optical NDT. This paper was further developed in [10], which proposed an architecture for creating an optical NDT. Another paper proposes Open Network Operating System (ONOS)[11] and uses NETCONF to control the transponders and gather telemetry data from them. An optical line system (OLS) that is responsible for transmitting data over the fiber optic network, and the OLS domain controller gathers telemetry data from the OLS and provides it to the ONOS controller. A shallow artificial neural network (ANN) accomplishes ML-based failure localization. ML is used to analyze the telemetry data and detect potential failures or anomalies in the network.

The authors in [12] have proposed optical network operations automation use cases enabled by a transmission performance-focused Digital Twin. These include provisioning automation, transmission performance risk mapping, optimization-based planning and control, and generalized optical margin reduction. The authors in [13] present another intriguing approach. They propose a multifactor-associated network topology portrait (NTP) scheme, which offers a dynamic, real-time, and comprehensive representation of the topology for optical NDT.

The present study builds upon previous research on architecture supporting optical NDT and offers a comprehensive SDN controller architecture that can deliver the required workflows for optical NDT. We have extended the previously proposed architecture with new component DT entity manager to handle virtualization technologies and the role of NFV orchestrator in the NDT architecture. To the best of our knowledge, this paper presents the first approximation to optical digital twinning using virtualization technologies. Moreover, the authors present novel workflows for deploying and updating NDT, and present a validation of the suggested architecture using the ADRENALINE testbed and its counterpart Digital Twin based in virtualization technologies. The different NDT lifecycle phases are analyzed and evaluated.

The remaining sections of this paper are structured as follows. In Section II, we introduce the proposed solution for a cloud-native SDN controller and discuss its internal architecture and key features for supporting Network Digital Twins. Section III outlines the experimental validation process and the obtained results. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper and provides insights on future research directions.

II. ARCHITECTURE FOR AN SDN CONTROLLER TO SUPPORT NETWORK DIGITAL TWIN

In Figure 2, a reference architecture is presented for an SDN controller. This architecture lays the foundation for a modular NDT architecture that allows third-party developers to develop and connect custom data models that augment NDT functionality. The NDT architecture takes into account the need for an orchestrator (such as an NFV orchestrator) to deploy the virtualized environment for NDT. The modular architecture for the SDN controller has been described in [2].

Relevant to NDT, it comprises several components: a) Digital Twin Entity Manager; b) Cloud orchestrator client; c) Data Collector; d) Monitoring; e) Context database, f) Service, and g) Device. The following subsections describe these necessary components that are designed as micro-services following cloud-native principles.

Fig. 2. Proposed Architecture for an SDN controller to support Network Digital Twin

- The Digital Twin Entity Manager (DTEM) is responsible for managing NDT, keeping track of its life-cycle, and controlling various NDT elements through a virtualization platform, such as a cloud infrastructure. The DTEM interfaces with the cloud orchestration client, which deploys and configures NDT virtual entities with data collected and interpreted by the DTEM. Service Mapping Models (SMM) provide data model instances for different network applications, enhancing network service agility and programmability. Our proposed optical NDT incorporates basic models and functional models. Basic models refer to the optical network elements and their topological and status information, including transponders, allocated and available DWDM channels, operational state, to complete the real-time accurate characterization of the real optical network. Moreover, functional models refer to various data models used for network analysis and forecasting.
- The cloud orchestrator client facilitates the interaction with a cloud orchestrator, such as an NFV orchestrator, to deploy virtualized entities of the NDT. Each virtual entity represents an NDT node, link, or abstracted network topology, and can be dynamically deployed and configured. Cloud orchestrator is also responsible to map the received data to the optical NDT through configuration of the modelled optical nodes and links.
- The data collector component is responsible for collecting the data necessary for deploying and updating NDT. The data collector is based on event publish/subscribe mechanisms, such as the Kafka data broker [14]. The Semantic Data Aggregator (SDA) is a possible solution that can be incorporated into the data collector to include data context in the expected data models. The SDA is a

data engineering platform that enables the exchange of data between data sources and data consumers [15].

- Monitoring includes an alarm manager and a subscription manager, offering subscription capabilities to the other components of the SDN controller.
- Context is the internal SDN controller data repository that composes and updates the topological and connectivity views of the physical optical network, including allocated and available optical resources.
- Service manages the life-cycle of connectivity services via a plugin-based service handler API that supports different data models, configuration protocols and service types. It includes multiple interfaces, such as IETF L2/L3 VPN, or ONF Transport API. It is able to provide optical connectivity services.
- Device interacts with the networking equipment or network systems through a plugin-based driver API which allows developers to implement protocols and data models for different device types, including P4, OpenConfig, ONF Transport API and mmWave devices.

A use case for an optical digital twin network is the analysis of the quality of transmission (QoT). The optical digital twin network would create a virtual replica of the physical fiber optic network, capturing its characteristics in real-time. By incorporating QoT analysis, the digital twin network can simulate and assess the quality of data transmission across the network, considering factors such as signal strength, attenuation, dispersion, and noise. This use case would enable network operators and engineers to proactively monitor and troubleshoot potential issues before they impact actual data transmission. Additionally, the digital twin network can facilitate advanced analytics and predictive maintenance. By continuously collecting data from the physical network and analyzing it in the digital twin environment, operators can identify patterns and trends, such as link degradation, that may affect transmission quality. This knowledge can help in planning network upgrades, capacity expansions, or routing optimizations to maintain high-quality transmission performance. Another use case for an optical digital twin network is in the design and planning of new fiber optic networks or expansions of existing networks.

In our proposed architecture, during the initialization stage, the network digital twin (NDT) typically begins with a basic representation of the network's topology. This initial version of the NDT may include information about the network's structure, such as the nodes (network elements) and the links connecting them. The topology provides a foundational understanding of how the network is organized and interconnected. However, as the NDT evolves and undergoes deployment phase, it can incorporate more detailed models of the equipment present in the optical network. These detailed models go beyond the simple topology and include specific characteristics, parameters, and behaviors of individual network elements, such as optical switches, routers, transceivers, or amplifiers. Data will flow to the data collector, which collects relevant information about the network's state, performance, and other operational aspects. The data collector gathers data

from various sources, such as network monitoring tools, performance metrics, configuration information, and potentially other external data feeds. The collected data is then processed, analyzed, and used to populate and refine the models within the NDT. The models can be built using techniques such as machine learning, statistical analysis, or other data-driven approaches. The data helps to calibrate and validate the models, enabling the NDT to accurately represent the behavior and characteristics of the network and its components.

The NDT update phase of the optical NDT involves reconfiguring the NDT to reflect changes in the physical network. The mechanism of reconfiguration can vary depending on the specific implementation and requirements of the NDT system. Machine learning techniques can be employed as part of the reconfiguration process, but they are not the only approach. In our case, an update of the node and link parameters is provided through DTEM. Machine learning techniques can play a role in analyzing the data and identifying patterns, correlations, or anomalies. This analysis can inform the reconfiguration process by suggesting adjustments to the NDT models or parameters. For example, machine learning algorithms can be used to predict network behavior, optimize resource allocation, or identify potential failures.

Fig. 3. NDT life-cycle management sequence diagram

The sequence diagram in Figure 3 illustrates the various components involved in the life-cycle of NDT. The presented workflow takes into account an SDN-based optical network with an Optical Line System (OLS) SDN controller and a per-node SDN agent. For NDT deployment, a cloud-native SDN controller implementing the proposed architecture is used. The diagram also incorporates an NFV orchestrator (NFV-O) to install the virtualized elements needed to create the NDT. The life-cycle of NDT is comprised of five phases:

- 1) Initialization: Before deploying the NDT, the physical SDN controller (typically an OLS) must subscribe to a data collector (e.g., Kafka broker) to publish topological and connectivity data streams.

- 2) NDT Deployment: In this phase, the network operator requests the deployment of an NDT, which is then created using virtualization techniques.
- 3) NDT Update: The NDT is updated with real-time data obtained from the physical network, thereby ensuring that it reflects the current state of the network.
- 4) NDT Operation: This phase allows the network operator to perform what-if scenarios and feasibility studies, such as exploring the deployment of novel optical light-paths in the underlying physical network.
- 5) NDT Removal: Once the NDT is no longer needed, all virtualized elements are removed and the physical SDN controller unsubscribes from the published data streams.

The first phase of the NDT life-cycle is the initialization phase, which is primarily concerned with setting up the subscription mechanisms necessary for data collection. In this phase, the physical SDN controller is connected to the Data Collector's publish/subscribe mechanism (step 1), which is typically implemented using a Kafka broker. However, it could also be part of the SDA introduced earlier. The purpose of this connection is to enable the publication of topological and connectivity data streams that will be used by the NDT in subsequent phases.

In the next phase, the NDT deployment phase, a user requests the deployment of an NDT (step 2), which triggers the subscription of DTEM to Data Collector (step 3). This allows DTEM to receive all the published stream-record updates from the OLS controller, including node and link updates. Step 4 involves a complete update of all topological elements that are under the control of the OLS SDN controller, including nodes and links. The complete stream-record is processed in a loop, first focusing on all detailed nodes and then links. These updated information is disseminated internally within the cloud-native SDN controller (steps 5-7). DTEM is responsible for deploying and configuring a virtual node for each physical node, and configuring a virtual link for each physical link based on the received stream-records. Once these operations are complete, the optical NDT is ready to operate. The specific operations required to deploy the NDT depend on the technology being used, as shown in steps 8-10. An NFV orchestrator (NFV-O) is used to deploy the NDT, through the SDN controller cloud orchestrator client.

During the NDT update phase, SDN agents notify the OLS controller of events, such as link failure (step 11), and later, the physical OLS controller publishes updates about any changes in the network topology or connectivity (step 12). These updates are received by the Data Collector, which distributes them to the monitoring module (step 13). The monitoring module then stores the updates in the Context (step 14) and triggers the cloud-native recovery mechanism to ensure the network stays up and running. The Data Collector also notifies DTEM about the updates (step 15), which triggers the necessary re-configuration of the affected NDT. This involves updating the virtual nodes and links in the NDT to reflect the current state of the physical network. This update process is shown in steps 16-18 of the life-cycle, and is crucial to ensure the NDT remains accurate and useful for network operators.

During the operation phase of the optical NDT, a Connec-

tivity Service (CS) can be tested through the NDT (step 19). The feasibility of the CS can be evaluated using a Quality of Transmission (QoT) estimator or other similar methods, as described in steps 20-22. If the CS is feasible, it can be applied to the physical network (steps 23-26), which will result in an update of the NDT through the previously detailed NDT update mechanism (steps 11-18). This ensures that the NDT accurately reflects the current state of the physical network and allows for efficient and effective testing and deployment of connectivity services.

The last phase of the life-cycle is NDT removal, which is triggered by the user requesting it (step 27). This will free up the virtualization resources used by the NDT (steps 28-29), and DTEM will unsubscribe from the Data Collector streams (step 30). This will ensure that the resources used by the NDT are properly released and can be used for other purposes, and also that DTEM is no longer receiving updates for the NDT that has been removed.

The NDT is established along with and updated within the life-cycle of the optical network. The NDT created by virtualization techniques could be dynamically deployed and tear down to save resources. However, the virtualization techniques to create an accurate NDT could be cost-demanding in time. To this end, Section III evaluates the necessary time to deploy an optical NDT of a basic optical topology.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

This section outlines the experimental evaluation of the NDT deployment and operation architecture. The physical optical network used in the experiment is a hybrid fixed/flexi-grid DWDM core network, comprising 4 whitebox ROADMs/OXC nodes, sliceable-bandwidth variable transceivers (S-BVTs), and 5 bidirectional amplified optical links with a maximum length of 150 km (totaling 610 km of G-652 and G.655 SMF). The links support 100GHz CS, 50 GHz CS, or flexi-grid using commercially available WSS. The OLS controller, as shown in Fig. 2, provides ONF Transport API 2.1.3 and ONF TAPI streaming [4]. The network element agents implement the front-end towards the OLS using either the OpenROADM device model or a REST interface with JSON. We have used Mininet-Optical as virtualization tool, which is an extension of Mininet specifically designed for optical network simulation and emulation. Mininet is a widely used emulator for software-defined networks and provides a virtual environment to test and evaluate different network scenarios.

The proposed NDT deployment and operation architecture utilizes the ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) as the cloud-native SDN controller [2]. The TFS micro-service architecture provides an interface for easy integration of new micro-services, which enables the development of novel components for DTEM and cloud orchestrator client. The use of a Kafka broker as a Data Collector allows real-time data to flow from the physical network to the network digital twin. The ONF Transport API was extended to provide network telemetry information based on information streams to support this objective [4]. The publish/subscribe event bus architecture of the Kafka broker offers several benefits, as discussed in [14].

The ONF TR-548 standard provides a streaming mechanism that enables the provision of information from one system to another in a steady and continuous flow based on an event source/server streaming mechanism.

Log record for link information update is described in [4]. It allows for compacted log capability, enabling alignment with the current state from the provided stream. The client can achieve eventual consistency by connecting to the relevant streams. The log record body includes generalized content and is augmented with specific content based on the value of the control property, record-content (such as Link content in the example provided). Specific content definition can be provided as necessary.

To support the experimental evaluation of the proposed NDT deployment and operation architecture, a Mininet-Optical emulated network has been dynamically deployed and configured through an NFV orchestrator using the information received from the physical network through the ONF Transport API streams. DTEM subscribes to specific data streams and receives log records, which it analyses and stores in the data repository (Context). Received data streams might include either topological, operational or monitoring information, regarding specific nodes, transponders, or even link optical channels. DTEM takes responsibility for managing the lifecycle of NDT. The links and nodes in the Mininet-Optical network are updated with the latest information received from the OLS SDN controller. Mininet-Optical has launched the emulation using the defined topology and configuration. The emulation creates virtual instances of the network nodes, emulates optical links, and emulates the behavior of the optical network based on the specified parameters. During the emulation, various performance metrics can be monitored, such as signal quality. These metrics will provide insights into the behavior and performance of the optical network. This analysis helps in identifying potential performance bottlenecks or optimizing network configurations. With our proposed approach, we use a cloud-native SDN controller together with emulation capabilities of Mininet-Optical to obtain a digital twin of an optical network. The digital twin will provide a replica of the network, allowing to assess its behavior, evaluate performance, and perform various analyses without impacting the actual physical network.

The setup and tear down cumulative distribution function (CDF) for deploying and configuring the necessary NDT virtualized elements using NFV-O and mininet is shown in Figure 4. The results, based on 100 measurements, indicate that NDT deployment and configuration takes an average of 2.38 seconds, with a standard deviation of 0.9s. These measurements were taken from the reception of the NDT create/delete request until the NDT was created/deleted. On the other hand, for NDT tear down, the average time is around 0.85s, with a standard deviation of 0.26s. The cumulative step histogram in Figure 4 reveals that the variance is low, but these times can be influenced by the topological view of the physical optical network.

To evaluate the responsiveness of the NDT to various network events, we conducted several experiments. The first experiment involved simulating a node outage by cutting off

Fig. 4. CDF for NDT setup and teardown delays

Fig. 5. CDF of NDT update of events (node down, link bandwidth change, link failure)

the power to a node in the physical network. The OLS was able to notify the removal of the node, and we measured the time it took for the deployed NDT to be reconfigured with the latest data. The average delay for this event was found to be 0.96s, with a standard deviation of 0.52s.

Next, we simulated a degradation of bandwidth on an optical link. We measured the time it took for the NDT link bandwidth to be updated after the OLS notified the bandwidth degradation caused by frequent channel allocation. The average delay for this event was 0.03s, with a standard deviation of 0.01s.

Lastly, we removed a fiber link from the physical network and measured the time it took for the link to be removed from the NDT after being notified by the OLS. The average delay for this event was found to be 0.009s, with a standard deviation of 0.003s.

The cumulative distribution functions (CDF) for the delay times for the three events are shown in Figure 5. The plot

shows that the delay for updating the NDT with removed nodes is significantly higher than the other two events.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has proposed an architecture for ease of deployment of NDT with the usage of a cloud-native SDN controller, which is able to interact with physical SDN controllers. New cloud-native SDN controllers have been proposed, designed and validated and results are presented in terms of feasibility of the proposed solution and the deployment/tear down delays for NDT, as well as the delay to update NDT with novel network information, such as node removal, as well as link bandwidth update and link failure.

Additionally, future work should also focus on exploring the potential of NDTs in supporting network automation and optimization, as well as their integration with other emerging technologies such as edge computing, blockchain, and quantum computing.

An important area of research is the development of more advanced NDT models that can provide higher levels of abstraction, enabling network operators to model and simulate complex network scenarios and predict the impact of changes before they are deployed in the real network. Moreover, other significant metrics should be evaluated, such as the accuracy of the NDT relative to the physical network status.

Finally, the standardization of NDT models and interfaces is crucial to enable interoperability and the integration of NDTs with other network management and orchestration systems. Therefore, standardization bodies such as the IETF should continue to play a key role in the development of NDT technology and its integration with existing and emerging network technologies.

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